

FIGURE S1: Variability of gut microbiota composition in Metsim samples.....	2
FIGURE S2: Association of bacterial diversity and richness measures with traits.....	3
FIGURE S3: Associations of OTUs with fasting blood levels of metabolites.....	4
FIGURE S4: Boxplots of glutamine and branched chain amino acid (BCAA) levels	5
FIGURE S5: Correlation heatmap demonstrating the association between the metabolic traits and fasting TMAO concentrations.....	6
FIGURE S6: Gut microbiota profile in obese and type 2 diabetes.....	7
FIGURE S7: Comparison between preT2D and NGS OTU networks	8-9

Figure S1: Variability of gut microbiota composition in Metsim samples. Columns represent the relative abundance of microbial phyla on 538 Finnish males (A) and relative abundance of microbial family on 13 replicated samples (B). The average relative abundance for the top ten most prevalent bacterial family (C).

A.

B.

C.

Figure S2: Association of bacterial diversity and richness measures with traits. The heatmap shows the spearman correlation of each trait with alpha, richness (observed number of OTUs) and Shannon's index of diversity (A). The color key for correlation is shown. Significant differences in bacteria diversity and richness between groups with different HbA1c, glutamine and acetate levels (FDR<0.05)(B). Groups are divided as high or low based on mean metabolite concentrations.

A.

B.

Figure S3: Associations of OTUs with fasting blood levels of metabolites. Significant associations of

circulating serum metabolites with gut microbiota OTUs (shared 50% of subjects) at FDR<0.05. Associations were

adjusted for age and treatment.

Figure S4: Boxplots of glutamine and branched chain amino acid (BCAA) levels in subjects with low and high BMI (A) and subjects in different HOMA-IR levels (B). *P* values were obtained using Tukey's HSD test of significance.

A.

B.

Figure S5: Correlation heatmap demonstrating the association between the metabolic traits and fasting TMAO concentrations. Coloring represents the Spearman correlation coefficient between TMAO and traits. FDRs are denoted: *, FDR < 0.01; **, FDR < 0.001.

Figure S6: Gut microbiota profile in obese and type 2 diabetes. Boxplot of β diversity distances

(unweighted UniFrac) between microbial communities (A), Ratio of Firmicutes to Bacteroidetes individuals in different BMI classes (BMI<25, BMI 25-30 and BMI>30 and between individuals based on glucose tolerance test (NGT, preT2D and newT2D) (B). Boxplot of HOMA-IR and glycoprotein acetyls levels between individuals based on oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) (C). * $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.001$ for Tukey HSD test. OGTT descriptions see Methods.

A.

B.

C.

Figure S7: Comparison between preT2D and NGS OTU networks

A: OTU Co-occurrence networks for preT2D or NGS individuals. OTU (nodes) are colored by their corresponding WGCNA module colors. Edges are represented only for significant correlation between 2 OTU (P-value <0.01, abs (cor)>0.3). In both networks OTU are at the same locations. Network layout was based on OTU co-occurrence in preT2D condition.

B: Module-trait association: each cell of the matrix contains the correlation between one OTU module and a metabolic trait, and the corresponding p-value. The table is color-coded by correlation according to the color legend (red for positive correlations and green for negative correlations). Only traits associated with at least one module were represented (P-value<0.01).

C. Zsummary statistics of module preservation of preT2D OTU modules in NGS OTU modules (y-axis) vs. module size (x-axis). Green dashed line corresponds to the cutoff for very weak preservation and the blue one to no preservation. D. Heatmap of the correlations between OTU abundance in tan module and glucose level in preT2D and NGS individuals. Circles sizes are proportional to correlation values. Scatterplot is represented for OTU 186090 in preT2D and NGS conditions.

A.

preT2D - OTU network

NGS - OTU network

B.

Module-trait relationships

Module-trait relationships

C.

Preservation Zsummary

D.

correlation with glucose level

WGCNAModule

Family

f_Ruminococcaceae

o_Clostridiales

Genus

f_Ruminococcaceae

g_Oscillospira

g_Ruminococcus

o_Clostridiales

preT2D (corr=0.31 pvalue=9.79e-05)

NGS (corr=-0.006 pvalue=0.935)

